

WATER-INDUCED SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT OF EPOXY-BASED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

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1 General Introduction

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) have attracted considerable attention because of their distinct shape memory effect described the effect of restoring the original shape of a plastically deformed sample [1]. Recently, Huang *et al.* found that SMP composite [2] displayed water-driven shape memory effect. However, water-induced epoxy-based SMP has not been reported.

Epoxy-based SMP possesses excellent shape memory effect and can meet various practical needs by easily adjusting the chemical components, which make them have great potential applications in smart structures. This study constructs a novel epoxy-based SMP, which could change their mechanical properties upon exposure to water and display a good shape memory effect in response to water. This material is fabricated by introducing sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) into epoxy shape memory polymer. SDS is of an organosulfate containing a 12-carbon tail attached to a sulfate group, giving SDS the amphiphilic properties. Hence, it can be uniformly dispersed into epoxy shape memory polymer.

Herein, the shape recovery process of the composite carried out in water was investigated. Furthermore, a detailed mechanism for water-induced shape memory effect in this as-constructed epoxy-based shape memory polymer will be discussed. This study advocates the design concept and presents some experimental results of the water-induced smart composite.

2 Structural Characterizations

XRD is used to examine crystal phases of materials. **Figure 1A** shows that the XRD patterns of pure epoxy shape memory polymer (designated as ER), SDS and the composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER (designated as SDS-ER). It is

confirmed that the SDS (JCPDS file: 39-1996) and ER stably co-exist in the composite samples. The FT-IR spectrum of ER, SDS and SDS-ER is shown in **Figure 1B**. The SDS-ER shows absorptions at 1079 cm^{-1} and 1733 cm^{-1} respectively corresponding to the S=O stretching and the C=O stretching, which further supports the above XRD results.

Figure 1. XRD patterns (A) and FT-IR spectra (B): ER, SDS, and SDS-ER composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER.

3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

In the DMA measurements, the storage modulus and the tangent delta were recorded as a function of temperature. The DMA results show that the storage modulus and T_g of SDS-ER reduced comparing with ER (**Figure 2**). The T_g of ER and SDS-ER were $112\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $89\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

Figure 2. DMA curves of ER and SDS-ER composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER.

4 Water-Induced Shape-Memory Effect

The water-induced shape memory effect of SDS-ER composite has been exemplarily demonstrated in **Figure 3**. The rectangular SMP composite (permanent shape) sheet was bended into an “n” shape at 130 °C and retained this shape during cooling back to room temperature (about 25 °C). No apparent recovery was found after the deformed sample was kept in the water as can be shown in Figure 3 (0 min, 30 min and 60 min). However, water was applied for about 90 min, the composite sample starting conversion of the flexural shape to permanent shape had been completed within 180 min, where the dimensions of used specimen were 55 mm × 4 mm × 3 mm. The final shape was close to the original straight shape with some remaining flexion due to friction among the polymer chains.

Figure 3. The water-induced shape-memory effect of SDS-ER composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER at room temperature.

Notably, only SDS-ER composite shows good recovery properties in water, but it has no apparent recovery at atmosphere (**Figure 4**). The observation confirms that water molecules play a significant role in the shape memory effect.

Figure 4. The water-induced shape-memory effect at room temperature of ER and SDS-ER composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER.

To well understand the SDS effects on the water-induced shape memory behaviors, the XRD patterns

and FT-IR spectra of SDS-ER before and after dipping in water are displayed in **Figure 5**. Surprisingly, the results demonstrate that the content of SDS in the SDS-ER composite reduce after dipping, which might well be attributed to ion-exchange effect during dipping process causing microvoids formation on the surface of the sample. Furthermore, this phenomenon also could be enhanced by chemical interaction or physical swelling effect [3].

Figure 5. XRD patterns (A) and FT-IR spectra (B): SDS-ER composite prepared by introducing SDS into ER before dipping and after dipping.

5 Summary

In this paper, we present a facile fabrication of epoxy-based SMP and the composite shows better water-responsive shape memory effect at room temperature. With the further development and the emergence of novel epoxy-based SMP, the range of applications is expected to expand more widely in the near future.

References

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